

Bidirectional-Thruster Multirotor for Perimeter Pipe Inspections (BiMPPI): A Nonlinear Optimal Integral-SDRE Design

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel bidirectional-thruster multirotor for perimeter pipeline inspection (BiMPPI). The bidirectional thrusters enable the generation of negative collective thrust, allowing BiMPPI to land on the pipe, reverse motor thrust directions, and push against the pipe while rotating around it without losing physical contact. An integral state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) controller is used during the turning phase around the pipe. The integral SDRE controller is compared through simulations with the servo-SDRE controller, exhibiting similar performance while eliminating the need for an online solution to the SDRE. The platform is experimentally validated through indoor flights, demonstrating superior performance in rotational movements around a mockup pipeline compared to both SDRE and standard PID controllers.

Keywords: Bidirectional-thruster quadrotor, Rotation around pipe, Integral-SDRE, Servo design, UAV.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The application of multirotor aerial systems in industry has increased due to advances in commercialized equipment in drone manufacturing, autopilot designs, and rotor developments. Monitoring and inspection using unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is a hot topic divided into two categories of non-contact and contact inspection. Flight and recording videos and images [1, 2], using laser [3] and LiDAR sensors to map point clouds [4, 5], and radiation measurement [6, 7], are examples of non-contact inspection using multirotor UAVs. Contact inspection is more challenging since interaction with the environment causes disturbances to the aerial robot and changes the dynamics of the system [8]. In the last years, various solutions have been developed to address these challenges, including the

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integration of aerial manipulators [9, 10] to interact with their environment more effectively, and the design of more complex platforms [11, 12], which enhance the physical interaction capabilities beyond those of standard multirotor systems. These advances enable UAVs to perform a wider range of tasks that require physical interaction, such as maintenance, repairs, and sensor placement while maintaining stability and control during flight.

In the oil and gas industry, pipeline inspections are crucial for ensuring the safety and efficiency of operations. These inspections typically involve direct contact between the sensor and the pipeline surface. An example is wall thickness inspections, where ultrasonic sensors are used to measure the thickness of the pipeline at various points, detecting potential reductions in thickness due to corrosion. Conducting this type of inspection around the entire pipeline using UAVs can significantly reduce costs, time, and the risk of accidents [13]; however, it is challenging. A part of the HYFLIERS¹ project highlighted this interesting problem by presenting several prototypes and platforms. One approach involved a snake-like manipulator attached to a UAV for inspecting the lower parts of pipelines [14], where it was suggested to avoid rotating around the pipe and instead maintain the UAV in a stable position on the pipeline. A similar approach was presented in [15], where the proposed hybrid robot stays on the pipeline and uses a robotic arm to inspect the external surface of the pipeline. Other solutions, as the one developed within the PILOTING² project, involve the use of specific robotic crawlers that maintain contact with the pipeline surface through magnetic wheels and perform contact-based inspections using ultrasonic sensors [16]. These robots are transported, deployed, and retrieved by a UAV, enabling efficient and precise inspection operations. However, these robots are limited to pipelines without insulation, as insulated pipelines are typically covered with aluminum sheets, which are non-ferromagnetic.

There is a technical issue with the complete rotation of a UAV without any magnetic device or robotic arm around the pipeline, as it has to generate negative thrust force after landing to push against the pipeline and keep contact during the operation. This problem has been studied in the last years through simulations or experimental testbenches, without any complete experimental flight. The use of variable pitch rotors was proposed to generate collective thrust force in both positive and negative directions [17]; however, the flight was not reported. The concept was implemented on a testbench with a physical joint to keep the system rotating in a constrained motion during the regulation control. The application of the iterative learning control in the same setup showed a successful implementation of an optimal control learning method with experimental validation [18]. Other proposed controllers were validated through simulations [19], in which the system was modeled as a rotor-based inverted pendulum. This work provides a solution for rotating around a pipeline using a bidirectional-thrusters multirotor.

The design for motion control during rotational inspection could benefit from

¹<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/779411>

²<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871542>

many methods. Linear control techniques are widely used, including proportional-derivative (PD) controllers [20, 21] and proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers [22, 23]. However, controllers with feedforward terms offer significant advantages, particularly in motion prediction and control accuracy. Optimal control methods, which aim to minimize energy consumption while ensuring precise regulation and tracking [24], are particularly effective when the system model is well-defined. As the complexity of such models increases, learning-based techniques are often employed to avoid the need for precise modeling. For example, Duong et al. introduced a model-free optimal control method using reinforcement learning [25].

Furthermore, the state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) is a popular controller for pendulums and rotary systems. It is a nonlinear optimal method that can present a trade-off between precision and energy consumption [26, 27]. Design flexibility is one of the important characteristics of the SDRE controller. This flexibility comes from the nonlinear structure of the weighting matrices. Since they accept states, then soft constraints [28], obstacle avoidance terms [29, 30], adaptive design [31, 32], can be considered as the objective of the design. Systematic design and derivation of the SDRE allow easy modification of the method. For example, adding integration of tracking states to the control law results in a servo-SDRE design [33, 34, 35]. The servo design adds an integrator to the controller, which eliminates the steady-state error in the response, potentially caused by external disturbances, signal measurement noise, or modeling mismatches.

Similarly, other advanced techniques in control engineering effectively address disturbances and model uncertainties. Specifically, the state-filtered disturbance rejection control proposed in [36] compensates for both matched and mismatched uncertainties without requiring them to be continuously differentiable. Likewise, to improve the accuracy of disturbance measurement, multilayer neural networks can be employed to approximate endogenous disturbances [37]. In this work, disturbances during the rotation around the pipeline are rejected using a SDRE design through the integrator. This approach eliminates the steady-state error while minimizing energy consumption, thanks to the optimal SDRE controller.

The solution method to the SDRE control is numerical in the majority of the case studies, especially when the systems possess many degrees of freedom (DoFs). The rotation mode of the inspection proposes a single-DoF motion which suggests the usage of an exact solution approach to solve the SDRE. The exact solution approach can be implemented offline which is an advantage for practical tests [17]. In this approach, offline computations are performed outside the control loop (only once) based on the system's physical characteristics. Then, during operation, the control law only updates the states using the precomputed gains [38, 39]. When solving the Riccati equation offline, multiple roots exist, and selecting the correct root that ensures a symmetric positive definite solution requires careful consideration. The Lyapunov method was used to determine the correct signs of the gain components for a single-degree-of-freedom (DoF) system, ensuring stability and accuracy [40].

Figure 1: The BiMPPI during a rotation around a PVC pipeline. Two motors change of spinning direction to generate more roll torque.

1.2. Contributions and Novelties

In this work, we present BiMPPI, a “Bidirectional-thruster Multirotor for Perimeter Pipe Inspections”. The BiMPPI is capable of controlled rotational maneuver around a pipeline by using bidirectional motors, as shown in Figure 1. This platform enhances the possibility of using standard multi-rotors for perimeter pipeline inspections without the need for any complex mechanical design in the landing gear or the use of magnetic parts. Main contributions:

1. Design, manufacturing, and experimental validation of a novel bidirectional-thruster multirotor UAV for perimeter pipe inspections.
2. Theoretical and experimental development of a nonlinear optimal SDRE controller for the complete rotation around the pipe.

To the best of our knowledge, the BiMPPI is the first aerial platform capable of performing a complete rotational movement around a pipeline without relying on magnetic devices, fixtures, or complex mechatronic designs to maintain contact with the pipeline. Instead, the BiMPPI relies on bidirectional rotors, achieved through the use of reversible electronic speed controllers (ESCs) and 3D propellers, which can rotate in both directions. Bidirectional rotors have been extensively used in recent years to enhance the interaction capabilities of aerial multi-rotors, such as developing omnidirectional platforms [41, 42]. In our case, the bidirectional rotors allow the BiMPPI to generate negative thrust once it lands on the pipeline, ensuring contact during the rotational movement. Additionally, they allow generating larger roll torque to control rotation. Compared with platforms based on unidirectional thrusters, the BiMPPI offers a greater control range

due to the use of bidirectional thrusters. Furthermore, they also enable the possibility of performing various types of operations, as the platform can execute reverse flights. In this work, the BiMPPI performs three types of operations: top-to-bottom inspection, bottom-to-top inspection, and full perimeter inspection. In the first two cases, the platform needs to perform both normal and reverse flights, as the BiMPPI rotates only half of the perimeter. These types of operations are required when there is a wall or obstacles along the pipeline that prevent full rotation, as can be the case with a pipe rack. Due to this, the BiMPPI is equipped with two landing gears, one on the bottom and another on the top. In addition, the rotational inspections of this work are limited to horizontal pipelines, which allows us to neglect the dynamics along the pipeline axis, as there is no force projected in that direction, and equilibrium is achieved. Due to this, our system is analyzed as a one-DoF system during the rotational movement. High-tilted or vertical pipeline inspections, where the gravity force is projected along the pipeline axis and the equilibrium is no longer guaranteed, are proposed as future work.

Compared to other solutions that rely on multirotors with robotic arms [15], our approach prioritizes simplicity and a lightweight design, eliminating the need for complex mechanical or mechatronic systems. The BiMPPI is suitable for both isolated pipelines and pipeline racks, provided there is sufficient lateral space for the multirotor to rotate around the pipeline. When lateral obstacles, such as walls or narrow pipeline racks, prevent full rotation, alternative solutions based on snake-arm robots, such as those proposed in [14], can be employed. However, like the BiMPPI, these solutions also require a minimum distance to ensure that the robotic arm can reach the lower part of the pipeline while the platform remains positioned above.

Due to the nonlinear dynamics of the rotational movement around the pipeline, the controller is developed based on the SDRE. In addition, the usage of an integrator was necessary to achieve acceptable performance in the rotation control, as the experimental validation of the platform can cause steady-state error due to disturbances. In this work, we use a servo-SDRE-based design, where an exact solution approach is used to control the system experimentally. However, the servo structure increases the dimension of the system and makes the exact solution more complex. Then a comparison is performed between the two following cases: servo SDRE with numerical solution, and SDRE plus an integrator using an exact solution approach. The simulation results show that the performance of the methods match and can be considered for the experimental tests.

1.3. Outline

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the theoretical background for the SDRE control method. Then, the mathematical modeling of the system is presented in Section 3, while the complete control framework is included in Section 4. Section 5 describes the setup, communication, and experimental equipment of the BiMPPI. The experimental results are reported in Section 6, where the platform is validated through indoor flights. Finally, the conclusions of this work, along with future research directions, are summarized in Section 7.

2. Theoretical Background: Servo SDRE Control Structure

The traditional SDRE design does not provide an integrator; hence, mismatch in modeling, disturbance from the environment, or noise in the measurement can cause steady-state error in the control output. Augmenting an integrator eliminates the steady-state error, modifies the SDRE behavior, and shows robust characteristics. This section presents the SDRE governing equations, augmentation of the integrator, the so-called “servo-SDRE” formulation, and the exact solution to single-DoF systems.

2.1. The SDRE

Consider a nonlinear differential equation, time-invariant and affine-in-control, as in the following form:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) + \mathbf{E}_d \mathbf{d}(t), \quad (1)$$

where state variables are gathered in $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and all input signals in $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $\mathbf{d}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is a disturbance vector to the system, $\mathbf{E}_d = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{(n-m) \times m} \\ \mathbf{I}_{m \times m} \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ includes the dynamics of the system, i.e. inertia, gravity, Coriolis/centrifugal terms, etc., and $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ the coefficients of the inputs. $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ and $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t))$ are vector-valued, smooth, piecewise-continuous functions and satisfy the local Lipschitz condition. The equilibrium point of the system is considered zero $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{0}$. The nonlinear system (1) must be transformed into an apparent linearization representation. In order to do this, a state vector must be factored from $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ and an input vector from $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t))$. Then, it can be rewritten as state-dependent coefficient (SDC) parameterization [35]:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{E}_d \mathbf{d}(t), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ and $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are held.

Assumption 1. *A completely controllable SDC pair $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$ exists for all $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ in $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ [43].*

The optimal design is defined by the quadratic cost function integral in the infinite-horizon time domain [44]:

$$J(\cdot) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty [\mathbf{x}^\top(t) \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{u}^\top(t) \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{u}(t)] dt, \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$. In addition, $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{R}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) > \mathbf{0}$ penalizes the input signals and $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{Q}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \geq \mathbf{0}$ penalizes the state variables.

Assumption 2. *A completely observable pair of $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$ exists for all $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ in $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$, where $\mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ is the Cholesky decomposition of $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ [43].*

Applying the stationary optimality condition on the Hamiltonian function, the control law of the SDRE is obtained [44]:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t), \quad (4)$$

where the optimal gain $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{K}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) > \mathbf{0}$ of the control law is the solution to the state-dependent Riccati equation [44]:

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbf{A}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \\ &\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{0}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The controllability and observability of Assumptions 1 and 2 are guaranteed through checking the rank of the two following matrices:

$$\mathcal{M}_c = [\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \quad \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{A}^{n-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))],$$

and

$$\mathcal{M}_o = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \\ \mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{A}^{n-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \end{bmatrix}.$$

If the rank of \mathcal{M}_c and \mathcal{M}_o are full, then the SDRE can be solved. The sub-optimal gain $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ provides a stable controller for the optimal control problem.

Without loss of generality, to regulate the states to a desired condition rather than zero equilibrium point and adding an integrator, the control law (4) is rewritten as [18]:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{e}(t), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{x}_{\text{des}}(t)$ for trajectory tracking or $\mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{x}_{\text{des}}$ for point-to-point motion control. In this context, “des” refers to the desired quantities.

2.2. Servo Design

The sub-optimal gain of the SDRE controller $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))$, the solution to (5), is multiplied by the state-vector $\mathbf{x}(t)$ in control law (4) or error vector (6). The state variables are commonly the generalized coordinates and time-derivative of that, i.e. position and velocity in mechanical systems. Then the overall gain of the SDRE controller can be partitioned into two proportional $\mathbf{X}_P(\mathbf{x}(t))$ and derivative $\mathbf{X}_D(\mathbf{x}(t))$ sub-blocks as:

$$\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = [\mathbf{X}_P(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{X}_D(\mathbf{x}(t))] = \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)).$$

The SDRE performs properly for general nonlinear systems in theory and simulations; however, in practice and experimentation, an integrator is needed to add robustness, reduce the steady-state error, and compensate for the mismatch in modeling.

Consider that the nonlinear system (1) must track a trajectory through a set of desired variables $\mathbf{r}_c(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ (the reference trajectory could be constant \mathbf{r}_c) [43]:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_T(t) - \mathbf{r}_c(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_N(t) \end{bmatrix},$$

where $\mathbf{x}_N(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n-p}$ collects the remaining state variables. To present the servo SDRE and add the integrator, the state vector is extended as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t) = [\mathbf{x}_I^\top(t), \mathbf{x}_T^\top(t), \mathbf{x}_N^\top(t)]^\top, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_I(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the integral of the states in $\mathbf{x}_T(t)$ [43]. Adding the integral of some states to the state vector, Eq. (7), modifies the SDC parameterization as:

$$\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}}(t) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{p \times p} & \mathbf{E}_{p \times n} \\ \mathbf{0}_{n \times p} & \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \end{bmatrix}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}(t))} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{p \times m} \\ \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \end{bmatrix}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{x}(t))} \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{E}_I \mathbf{d}(t), \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{E} = [\mathbf{I}_{p \times p}, \mathbf{0}_{p \times (n-p)}]$, $\mathbf{E}_I = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{(p+n-m) \times m} \\ \mathbf{I}_{m \times m} \end{bmatrix}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(p+n) \times m}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(p+n) \times (p+n)}$. It also changes the cost function (3) into [43]:

$$J_{\text{servo}}(\cdot) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty [\tilde{\mathbf{x}}^\top(t) \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{u}^\top(t) \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{u}(t)] dt, \quad (9)$$

in which $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(n+p) \times (n+p)}$ penalizes the integrator plus other states. The SDRE equation for the servo version is modified based on the new matrices $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}(t))$, $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{x}(t))$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ in (8) and (9) to:

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \tilde{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \\ & \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \tilde{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \tilde{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{0}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Consequently, the SDRE control law (4) is updated as servo-SDRE:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}(t) &= -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \tilde{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_I(t) - \int_0^t \mathbf{r}_c(\tau) d\tau \\ \mathbf{x}_T(t) - \mathbf{r}_c(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_N(t) \end{bmatrix} \\ &= -\tilde{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_T(t) - \mathbf{r}_c(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_N(t) \end{bmatrix} - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_I(\mathbf{x}(t)) \left(\mathbf{x}_I(t) - \int_0^t \mathbf{r}_c(\tau) d\tau \right), \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is the proportional-derivative part of the control gain and $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_I(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times p}$ is the integral one.

Integral SDRE. The dimension of the servo-SDRE (10) is augmented, but the control law (11) releases the same m inputs in a vector with the addition of an integrator. So, the following change in the control law adds an equivalent integrator to the system without augmenting the size of the Riccati equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}(t) &= -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_T(t) - \mathbf{r}_c(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_N(t) \end{bmatrix} \\ &\quad - \mathbf{K}_I \left(\mathbf{x}_I(t) - \int_0^t \mathbf{r}_c(\tau) d\tau \right), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_I \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is the integral gain of the controller. The servo-SDRE control law (11) can be used for numerical solutions to the Riccati equation and integral

SDRE (12) can be used when an exact solution to single-DoF system is required. Both methods will be compared in Section 4.3.

The main advantages of the SDRE method are nonlinearity of the controller, optimal structure, and easy tuning. Despite the advantages of this technique, it is quite sensitive to model uncertainty and conventional SDRE design does not have any tool for disturbance rejection. To consider disturbance rejection, specific modifications could be considered in the structure of the SDRE to observe and compensate for it [45, 46], or expanding the structure using an integrator as a classical approach for disturbance compensation. Two ways to add an integrator to the SDRE are servo design and the integral SDRE, both presented in this subsection. Since the disturbance is moderate and offline solution is preferable for real time implementation, the integral SDRE is chosen as the control law. To show that the presented servo-SDRE is effective in disturbance rejection on the system's steady-state error, the simulation section presents the regulation of the system using a random disturbance vector with a small shift in the signal. The experimental results also confirm the integral SDRE's effectiveness compared to conventional controllers.

Remark 1. *Although the disturbance exists in the formulation of the system and compensated through the additional integrator, the focus of this work is nonlinear optimal control for the particular case of rotation around the pipe. The deep analysis of disturbance rejection is proposed for future study.*

2.3. Exact Solution to Single-DoF Systems

The most common solution method to the SDRE is numerical based on the Schur method [47], specifically when the system possesses many degrees of freedom. The matrix SDRE equation is symmetric and presents $\frac{n(n+1)}{2}$ coupled equations for a system for a state vector of size n . For a single-DoF system, the state vector possesses two components $n = 2$, and then there are three algebraic equations to be solved. Consider a second-order differential equation

$$\ddot{q}(t) = f(q(t), \dot{q}(t))q(t) + g(q(t), \dot{q}(t))u(t) + d(t), \quad (13)$$

with state-vector $\mathbf{x}(t) = [q(t), \dot{q}(t)]^\top$ and disturbance parameter $d(t) \in \mathbb{R}$. This results in a state-space representation:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ f(\mathbf{x}(t)) & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t))} \mathbf{x}(t) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ g(\mathbf{x}(t)) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))} u(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} d(t). \quad (14)$$

The weighting matrices for system (14) are $\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}(Q_{11}, Q_{22})$ and R . Substituting the system and weighting matrices into SDRE (5) results in:

$$Q_{11} + 2K_{12}(\mathbf{x}(t))f(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \frac{K_{12}^2(\mathbf{x}(t))g^2(\mathbf{x}(t))}{R} = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$K_{11}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + K_{22}(\mathbf{x}(t))f(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \frac{K_{12}(\mathbf{x}(t))K_{22}(\mathbf{x}(t))g^2(\mathbf{x}(t))}{R} = 0, \quad (16)$$

$$2K_{12}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + Q_{22} - \frac{K_{22}^2(\mathbf{x}(t))g^2(\mathbf{x}(t))}{R} = 0. \quad (17)$$

Substituting the matrices into (4), the input control law is rewritten as:

$$u(t) = -\frac{K_{12}(\mathbf{x}(t))g(\mathbf{x}(t))}{R}x_1(t) - \frac{K_{22}(\mathbf{x}(t))g(\mathbf{x}(t))}{R}x_2(t). \quad (18)$$

Solving (15) for $K_{12}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ results in

$$K_{12}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \frac{R \left(f(\mathbf{x}(t)) \pm \sqrt{\frac{Rf^2(\mathbf{x}(t)) + Q_{11}g^2(\mathbf{x}(t))}{R}} \right)}{g^2(\mathbf{x}(t))}. \quad (19)$$

Solving (17) for $K_{22}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ and substituting the solution (19) into that generate:

$$K_{22}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \pm \sqrt{\frac{R \left(2 \frac{R \left(f(\mathbf{x}(t)) \pm \sqrt{\frac{Rf^2(\mathbf{x}(t)) + Q_{11}g^2(\mathbf{x}(t))}{R}} \right)}{g^2(\mathbf{x}(t))} + Q_{22} \right)}{g^2(\mathbf{x}(t))}}. \quad (20)$$

Since in the control law (18) the term $K_{11}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ is not employed, there is no need to solve (16). Moreover, the control gain of the SDRE is positive definite, then the positive solution in (20) is chosen. Using the second method of Lyapunov, it was proven that the positive sign selection of the solution in (19) must also be selected [40], which finalizes the definition of the control gains (19) and (20) for input (18).

3. Mathematical Modeling

This section presents the dynamic model of the system during both the free-flight phase and the rotational inspection phase.

3.1. Free Flight Dynamics

For describing the free flight dynamics of the BiMPPI, we consider a world frame, denoted as \mathcal{F}_W , with its origin at O_W and axes \mathbf{x}_W , \mathbf{y}_W , and \mathbf{z}_W . Additionally, a body frame, \mathcal{F}_B , is defined at the quadrotor's center of mass, with axes \mathbf{x}_B , \mathbf{y}_B , and \mathbf{z}_B . Figure 2 illustrates the quadrotor with the frames \mathcal{F}_W and \mathcal{F}_B .

Let $\mathbf{p}(t) = [x(t), y(t), z(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denote the position of the quadrotor with respect to the world frame \mathcal{F}_W , while $\mathbf{v}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the linear velocity expressed in \mathcal{F}_W . The orientation of the quadrotor is described by the roll-pitch-yaw angle vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}(t) = [\phi(t), \theta(t), \psi(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$, which defines the rotation of \mathcal{F}_B relative to \mathcal{F}_W . This orientation is also represented by the rotation matrix ${}^W\mathbf{R}_B(\boldsymbol{\eta}(t))$. Additionally, $\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the angular velocity of the quadrotor relative to \mathcal{F}_W , expressed in \mathcal{F}_B . The state vector of the system $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{12}$ is given by $\mathbf{x}(t) = [\mathbf{p}^\top(t), \boldsymbol{\eta}^\top(t), \mathbf{v}^\top(t), \boldsymbol{\omega}^\top(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{12}$. The system's control input is $\mathbf{u}(t) = [T(t), \tau_\phi(t), \tau_\theta(t), \tau_\psi(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$, which includes the collective thrust $T(t)$ and the three torques generated by the four motors. With this setup, the system

Figure 2: Frames, position, attitude, and motor numeration of the BiMPPI. The motor-to-motor distances are denoted as $2L_x$ and $2L_y$; the robot presents an “X” shape quadrotor configuration.

dynamics can be represented in state-space form as $\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t))$, which is expressed by the following equations:

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) = \mathbf{v}(t), \quad (21a)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}(t) = \mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\eta}(t))\boldsymbol{\omega}(t), \quad (21b)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}(t) = \frac{1}{m}({}^W\mathbf{R}_B(\boldsymbol{\eta}(t))T(t)\mathbf{z}_B - mg\mathbf{z}_W), \quad (21c)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}(t) = \mathbf{J}_B^{-1}(-\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) \times \mathbf{J}_B\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) + \boldsymbol{\tau}_R(t)), \quad (21d)$$

where $\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\eta}(t)) \in SO(3)$ is the transformation matrix that relates the angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\omega}(t)$ with the angle derivatives $\dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}(t)$, $\mathbf{J}_B \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the inertia matrix of the quadrotor, $m \in \mathbb{R}^+$ its mass and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R(t) = [\tau_\phi(t), \tau_\theta(t), \tau_\psi(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ includes the control torques.

This model represents the general dynamics of an aerial platform. The main difference between the different designs is in the generation of the collective thrust $T(t)$ and torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R(t)$ by the rotors. The control input $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is related to the rotor forces $\mathbf{F}(t) = [f_1(t), f_2(t), f_3(t), f_4(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$ by the allocation matrix $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$ as $\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{F}(t)$:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} T(t) \\ \tau_\phi(t) \\ \tau_\theta(t) \\ \tau_\psi(t) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{u}(t)} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ L_y & -L_y & L_y & -L_y \\ -L_x & -L_x & L_x & L_x \\ k_d & -k_d & k_d & -k_d \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{M}} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} f_1(t) \\ f_2(t) \\ f_3(t) \\ f_4(t) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{F}(t)}, \quad (22)$$

where $L_x \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $L_y \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are the motor-to-axis distances along \mathbf{x}_B and \mathbf{y}_B respectively (please see Figure 2), and $k_d = c_d/c_t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ relates the drag coefficient c_d and the thrust coefficient c_t of the propeller. The control force should satisfy $f_i(t) \in [f_{\min}, f_{\max}] \forall i = 1, \dots, 4$, where f_{\max} is the maximum force that can be generated by the motor and f_{\min} is the minimum force, that is typically $f_{\min} = 0$ for conventional multirotor UAVs based on unidirectional thrusters. However, in the case of the BiMPPI, by using bidirectional thrusters, the rotor forces can take values in $f_i(t) \in [-f_{\max}, f_{\max}] \forall i = 1, \dots, 4$. This allows for greater maneuverability and control, as the motors can exert both positive and negative forces, thereby

Figure 3: Generable roll torque τ_ϕ and collective thrust T for the multirotor with unidirectional motors, in red, and with bidirectional motors, in green. The use of bidirectional thrusters enables the generation of negative collective thrust as well as greater roll torque compared to the use of unidirectional thrusters.

Figure 4: The planer model of the robot during the constrained motion.

enabling the multirotor to achieve more complex movements and stabilization. In our case, we exploit this capability to enable the drone to roll around a pipeline in a controlled manner without requiring complex mechatronic designs. To achieve this, once the drone has landed on the pipe, the direction of the rotors' spin is reversed to generate a force against the pipe, ensuring contact during the operation. Additionally, the use of bidirectional rotors allows for the generation of greater torque τ_ϕ , allowing more precise control of the rotation around the pipeline. The maximum roll torque is given by $\tau_{\phi, \max} = 2L_y(f_{\max} - f_{\min})$. In the case of unidirectional motors $f_{\min} = 0$, while for bidirectional motors $f_{\min} = -f_{\max}$. This results in a maximum torque of $\tau_{\phi, \max}^{\text{Uni}} = 2L_y f_{\max}$ with unidirectional motors, while a maximum torque of $\tau_{\phi, \max}^{\text{Bi}} = 4L_y f_{\max}$ with bidirectional motors. Figure 3 represents the combination of rolling torque and thrust that can be generated with bidirectional motors and with unidirectional motors, showing bigger control capabilities by using bidirectional thrusters, in terms of negative collective thrust and higher roll torques.

3.2. Constrained Motion Dynamics

When the BiMPPI lands on the pipe, the dynamics of the six-DoF system, presented in Section 3.1, will be transformed into a single-DoF rotary motion,

constrained on a trajectory around the pipe, presented in Figure 4. The single-DoF second-order dynamics of the system is:

$$(mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})\ddot{\phi}(t) + mgr_{\text{ctr}} \sin \phi(t) = \tau_{\phi}(t) + \bar{d}(t), \quad (23)$$

where $\bar{d}(t) = (mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})d(t)$ is the scaled disturbance, and the produced input torque of the system by the propellers is $\tau_{\phi}(t) = L_y(f_1(t) - f_2(t))$ in which $f_1(t)$ and $f_2(t)$ are the bidirectional forces of the propellers, L_y is the motor-to-axis distance along the \mathbf{y}_B axis. Furthermore, r_{ctr} is the distance between the center of mass (CoM) of the BiMPPI and the center of the pipe, $(mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})$ is the moment of inertia of the system around pipeline axis, and $\phi(t)$ denotes the rotation of the drone around the pipe, the single generalized coordinate of the dynamics.

4. Control Framework

The proposed control framework of the BiMPPI consists of two main components: a cascade PID-based controller for the free-flight phase and an integral SDRE controller for the rotational phase.

4.1. Free Flight

The position controller computes the necessary force $\mathbf{f}_R(t)$ to follow the trajectory $\mathbf{p}_{\text{ref}}(t)$. We consider that this reference $\mathbf{p}_{\text{ref}}(t)$ is generated by an operator or a planner to go through a series of inspection points. In practice, this can be achieved using state-of-the-art path planning algorithms, as shown in [48], where a hybrid RRT* (Rapidly-exploring Random Tree) based algorithm computes the desired trajectory for a given set of inspection points while minimizing energy consumption.

To follow this reference trajectory $\mathbf{p}_{\text{ref}}(t)$, a cascade structure is used as follows:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}(t) = k_{\text{pp}}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \mathbf{p}(t)) + \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{ref}}(t), \quad (24a)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{\text{ref}}(t) = PD(\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t)) + \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{ref}}(t) + g\mathbf{z}_W, \quad (24b)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_R(t) = m\mathbf{a}_{\text{ref}}(t), \quad (24c)$$

where $k_{\text{pp}} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the proportional gain of the position loop, and $PD(\cdot)$ is the Proportional-Derivative control function of the velocity loop, composed by the porportional gain $k_{\text{pv}} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and the derivative gain $k_{\text{dv}} \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Then, the required thrust is computed as $T(t) = \|\mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}_B(\boldsymbol{\eta}(t))^\top \mathbf{f}_R(t)\|$. This force $\mathbf{f}_R(t)$ is also used with the reference yaw $\psi_{\text{ref}}(t)$, to obtain the reference angle $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\text{ref}}(t) = [\phi_{\text{ref}}, \theta_{\text{ref}}, \psi_{\text{ref}}]^\top$. The roll and pitch references are computed from the reference rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{\text{ref}} = [\mathbf{x}_r, \mathbf{y}_r, \mathbf{z}_r]$, as $\phi_{\text{ref}} = \arctan(r_{32}/r_{33})$ and $\theta_{\text{ref}} = -\arcsin(r_{31})$, where r_{ij} is the element (i, j) of the matrix \mathbf{R}_{ref} . The columns of the rotation matrix are computed using the required force \mathbf{f}_R as:

$$\mathbf{z}_r = \frac{\mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}_B^\top \mathbf{f}_R}{\|\mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}_B^\top \mathbf{f}_R\|}, \quad \mathbf{y}_r = \frac{\mathbf{z}_r \times [c_{\psi_r}, s_{\psi_r}, 0]^\top}{\|\mathbf{z}_r \times [c_{\psi_r}, s_{\psi_r}, 0]^\top\|}, \quad \mathbf{x}_r = \mathbf{y}_r \times \mathbf{z}_r, \quad (25)$$

where c_{ϕ_r} and s_{ψ_r} are the cosine and sine of the reference angle yaw ψ_{ref} respectively. The reference angle $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\text{ref}}(t)$ is controlled by a cascaded structure as:

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_{\text{ref}}(t) = \mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\eta}(t))^{-1}(k_{p\eta}(\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \boldsymbol{\eta}(t)) + \dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_{\text{ref}}(t)), \quad (26a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\zeta}_{\text{ref}}(t) = PD(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \boldsymbol{\omega}(t)), \quad (26b)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{\text{R}}(t) = \mathbf{J}_{\text{B}}\boldsymbol{\zeta}_{\text{ref}}(t) + \boldsymbol{\omega}(t) \times \mathbf{J}_{\text{B}}\boldsymbol{\omega}(t), \quad (26c)$$

where $k_{p\eta} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the proportional gain of the angles loop, and $PD(\cdot)$ is the Proportional-Derivative control function of the angles rate loop, composed by the porportional gain $k_{p\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and the derivative gain $k_{d\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ Finally, the required motor thrusts $\mathbf{F}(t)$ are computed as:

$$\mathbf{F}(t) = \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{u}(t), \quad (27)$$

where $\mathbf{u}(t)$ collects the control thrust $T(t)$ and the control torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{\text{R}}(t)$, and \mathbf{M}^{-1} is the inverse matrix of \mathbf{M} .

4.2. Rotational Movement around Pipeline

For the turning phase, the system (23) is rewritten as in the form of (13):

$$\ddot{\phi}(t) = - \underbrace{\frac{mgr_{\text{ctr}} \left[1 - \frac{\phi^2(t)}{6} + \frac{\phi^4(t)}{120} - \dots \right]}{mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}}}}_{f(\phi(t), \dot{\phi}(t))} \phi(t) + \underbrace{\frac{1}{mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}}}}_{g(\phi(t), \dot{\phi}(t))} \tau_{\phi}(t) + d(t), \quad (28)$$

where the Taylor series expansion of $\sin(\cdot)$ is used to factor one $\phi(t)$. The state vector is $\mathbf{x}(t) = [\phi(t), \dot{\phi}(t)]^{\top}$ and the SDC parameterization follows the form:

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{mgr_{\text{ctr}} \left[1 - \frac{\phi^2(t)}{6} + \frac{\phi^4(t)}{120} - \dots \right]}{mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}}} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}}} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Substituting the functions $f(\phi(t), \dot{\phi}(t))$ and $g(\phi(t), \dot{\phi}(t))$ from (28) into (19) and (20), the control law of the single-DoF dynamics (18) is built (arguments are not written for the sake of brevity):

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{\phi} = & - \left(\sqrt{\frac{Q_{11}}{(mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})^2} + \frac{Rg^2m^2r_{\text{ctr}}^2(\phi^4 - 20\phi^2 + 120)^2}{14400(mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})^2}} - \frac{gmr_{\text{ctr}}(\frac{\phi^4}{120} - \frac{\phi^2}{6} + 1)}{mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}}} \right) (mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})(\phi - \phi_{\text{ref}}) \\ & - \sqrt{\frac{Q_{22}}{R} + 2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{Q_{11}}{(mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})^2} + \frac{Rg^2m^2r_{\text{ctr}}^2(\phi^4 - 20\phi^2 + 120)^2}{14400(mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})^2}} - \frac{gmr_{\text{ctr}}(\frac{\phi^4}{120} - \frac{\phi^2}{6} + 1)}{mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}}} \right) (mr_{\text{ctr}}^2 + I_{\text{xx}})^2 (\dot{\phi} - \dot{\phi}_{\text{ref}})}. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

An integrator can be added to (29) to finalize the control law of the SDRE for practical implementation using the exact solution approach; the second approach is solving the servo-SDRE numerically and restructuring the input law as (11). Both (11) and (29) plus an integrator, can result in similar behavior with the specific tuning of weighting matrices. The advantage of the exact solution is the offline solution of the Riccati while the servo-SDRE needs an online solution at each timestep of the experiment. To show that the results of servo-SDRE (11) and integral SDRE (12) are close for single-DoF systems, simulations are presented in Subsection 4.3.

4.3. Simulations

This section simulates the presented model and compares the exact solution in Section 2.3 with the servo-SDRE design in Section 2.2. Consider the mass of the BiMPPI $m = 1.0454$ kg, the moment of inertia around the \mathbf{x}_B -axis $I_{xx} = 0.022$ kgm², gravity constant $g = 9.81$ m/s², and radius of rotation $r_{ctr} = 0.12$ m. The dynamics of the system are based on (23), subjected to a disturbance $d(t) = A_m(\text{rand}(1) - 0.5) + S_h$, where $A_m = 1$ is the amplitude of the disturbance, $S_h = 0.5$ is the shift, and $\text{rand}(1)$ generates a random number between $[0, 1]$ at each timestep of the simulation. The simulation time is considered to be $t_f = 10$ s. The initial condition of the system is $\mathbf{x}(0) = [0.3, 0]^T$ and the final one is the unstable equilibrium point of the system $\mathbf{x}(t_f) = [0, 0]^T$. Three controllers are compared, conventional SDRE with weighting matrices $\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}(1, 1.5)$, and $R = 1$, the servo-SDRE design with weighting matrices $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}} = \text{diag}(1, 1, 1.5)$, and $R = 1$, and exact solution to SDRE plus an integrator with weighting parameters $\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}(1, 1.5)$, $R = 1$ and $K_I = 1$.

Figure 5: The simulation results of the comparison between conventional SDRE, servo design, and SDRE plus an integrator. (a) Shows the convergence of the generalized coordinate. (b) Shows the angular velocity of the system in rotation. (c) Presents the input signals.

The results of the simulations and comparison are shown in Figure 5. The control gains were selected for the three controllers to perform a fair comparison, i.e., the same parameters for proportional and derivative tuning parameters and similar values for the gain of the integrators in the servo design and SDRE plus integrator. Figure 5-(a) shows the convergence of the generalized coordinate of the BiMPPI. The SDRE could not compensate for the external disturbance as expected, while both servo-SDRE and SDRE plus integrator design regulated to zero steady-state error. Integrators usually generate an overshoot in the signal which could be observed in Figure 5-(a). The velocity of the system in regulation is illustrated in Figure 5-(b) with the same performance for the three input laws. The cost of zero steady-state error using integrator is more energy consumption, as shown in Figure 5-(c).

4.4. Stability Discussion

As explained before, the entire inspection operation in this work consists of three phases: 1) flying to the pipe and landing, 2) rotating around the pipe, and 3) flying back to the ground station. The PID controller is active during the first

and third phases, while an integral SDRE controller is used during the second phase. Since there is a pause after landing on the pipe and before flying back to the ground station, with the quadrotor in a static condition, the switching between phases does not require stability analysis.

The flight stability of the cascade design for the free flight was provided and discussed in the literature [22, 49]. Here, we demonstrate it by combining the control law (24) and (26) with the equations of the model (21). Introducing the control force (24c) in the translational dynamics (21c), we obtain:

$$m\dot{\mathbf{v}}(t) = \cancel{\mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}_B(\boldsymbol{\eta}(t))} \underbrace{\|\mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}_B(\boldsymbol{\eta}(t))^\top \mathbf{f}_R(t)\|}_{T(t)} \underbrace{\frac{\mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}_B^\top \mathbf{f}_R}{\|\mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}_B^\top \mathbf{f}_R\|}}_{\mathbf{z}_B} - mg\mathbf{z}_W, \quad (30)$$

and consequently

$$m\dot{\mathbf{v}}(t) = \mathbf{f}_R(t) - mg\mathbf{z}_W, \quad (31)$$

which can be simplified by considering the expression of $\mathbf{f}_R(t)$ (24b) as:

$$m\ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) = m \underbrace{PD(\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t)) + \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{ref}}(t) + g\mathbf{z}_W}_{\mathbf{a}_{\text{ref}}(t)} - mg\mathbf{z}_W, \quad (32)$$

then

$$\ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) - \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{ref}}(t) = PD(\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t)). \quad (33)$$

Using the definition of the velocity reference (24a), we obtain:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) - \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{ref}}(t) = PD \underbrace{(k_{pp}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \mathbf{p}(t)) + \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t))}_{\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}(t)}. \quad (34)$$

Developing the PD function, (34) turns into:

$$-\ddot{\mathbf{e}}_p(t) = k_{pv}k_{pp}\mathbf{e}_p(t) + k_{pv}\dot{\mathbf{e}}_p(t) + k_{dv}k_{pp}\dot{\mathbf{e}}_p(t) + k_{dv}\ddot{\mathbf{e}}_p(t), \quad (35)$$

and be rewritten as

$$(k_{dv} + 1)\ddot{\mathbf{e}}_p(t) + (k_{pv} + k_{dv}k_{pp})\dot{\mathbf{e}}_p(t) + k_{pv}k_{pp}\mathbf{e}_p(t) = 0, \quad (36)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_p(t) = \mathbf{p}_{\text{ref}}(t) - \mathbf{p}(t)$. Finally, as $k_{pp}, k_{pv}, k_{pd} \in \mathbb{R}^+$, the position control loop is stable. To demonstrate the stability of the attitude control loop, a similar approach could be used, but now using the attitude dynamics (21d). Doing this, one can demonstrate that the attitude loop is stable as $k_{p\eta}, k_{p\omega}, k_{d\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

Regarding the second phase, the stability of the integral SDRE controller must be checked to guarantee the success of the inspection task. The stability of the conventional SDRE can be checked by defining a Lyapunov candidate in the form of $V(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{x}^\top(t)\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t)$. The following conditions must hold to have stability based on Lyapunov's second method:

- $V(\mathbf{x}(t)) = 0$ if and only if $\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{0}$,

- $V(\mathbf{x}(t)) > \mathbf{0}$ if and only if $\mathbf{x}(t) \neq \mathbf{0}$,
- $\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}(t)) < \mathbf{0}$ must hold for $\mathbf{x}(t) \neq \mathbf{0}$.

Considering that $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ is symmetric positive definite, the first and second conditions are satisfied. To check the third one, the derivative of the Lyapunov candidate is computed

$$\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \dot{\mathbf{x}}^\top(t)\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{x}^\top(t)\dot{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{x}^\top(t)\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t). \quad (37)$$

The design is in infinite-horizon SDRE, $t_f \rightarrow \infty$ in cost function integral (3), then $\dot{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$ and can be neglected in (37). Substituting system (2) and conventional SDRE control law (4) into (37), one can find (arguments are ignored for better presentation):

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} = & \mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{E}_d^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} \\ & - \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{E}_d \mathbf{d}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Replacing $-\mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}$ with $-\mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{x}$, Eq. (38) can be rewritten as:

$$\dot{V} = -\mathbf{x}^\top \{\mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{K}\} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{E}_d^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{E}_d \mathbf{d}, \quad (39)$$

which is a sign indefinite value. The first term satisfies

$$\mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{K} > \mathbf{0},$$

since \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{Q} are positive [43]; however, the contribution of the disturbance to the system $\mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{E}_d^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{K} \mathbf{E}_d \mathbf{d}$ avoids guaranteeing the stability analytically. To fix this instability issue in case of strong disturbance, servo-SDRE was suggested for the rotary pipe inspection problem in this work, presented in Section 2.2; however, the stability of the controller cannot be analytically proved using the Lyapunov's second method. The integral term presents sign-indefinite terms in the derivative of the Lyapunov candidate as well. Increasing \mathbf{Q} helps dominating the disturbance terms in case they possess negative signs, which is an extra tool to design a controller. Equation (39) shows that if the disturbance is negligible, the positive term can dominate the effect of it as is the case of this work (see Remark 1).

5. Experimental Platform Description

5.1. Platform Components

The aerial platform for experimental validation is based on the Micro FPV 250 V2 commercial frame, with a motor-to-axis distance of $L_x = 15$ cm and $L_y = 10$ cm along the \mathbf{x}_B axis and \mathbf{y}_B axis, respectively. The propulsive system is composed of the DYS Fire FPV Race Edition 2600KV Brushless motors, the nylon 5×3.0in 3D propellers, and the Hobbywing XRotor Micro 45A 4-in-1 ESC. Each motor is capable of generating a maximum thrust of $f_{\max} = 1.0$ kg when powered by a 4S

Figure 6: Main components of the BiMPPI.

LiPo battery. The quadrotor integrates as autopilot, the Raspberry Pi 3 Model B connected to the Emlid’s sensors shield Navio2. All the system is powered by a 4S 4000mAh LiPo battery. Figure 6 shows the components of the aerial platform, while Figure 7 shows a schematic of the connection between the components. Furthermore, Table 1 summarizes the main features of the BiMPPI. Although the payload capacity is relatively limited, it is sufficient to carry a lightweight camera for visual inspections around the pipeline. Moreover, BiMPPI aims to validate the novel use of bidirectional multirotors for rotating around pipelines, rather than carrying heavier inspection sensors such as Pulsed Eddy Current (PEC) or X-Ray, which would require a redesign of the platform to consider the weight of such sensors.

Table 1: Main features of the BiMPPI.

Parameter	Value
Weight/Payload	1.05/0.3 kg
Time of flight	12 min
$I_{xx}/I_{yy}/I_{zz}$	0.025/0.013/0.034 kg m ²
L_x/L_y	0.15/0.10 m
Propellers	3D Propellers 5×3.0 in
Brushless motors	DYS Fire FPV Race Edition 2600KV
LiPo Battery	4S, 4000mAh
f_{max}	1.0 kg
Autopilot	Raspberry Pi 3B + Navio2
Firmware	Ardupilot modified
Positioning System	OptiTrack

The selected ESC allows bidirectional control of the brushless motors. This

Figure 7: Schematic of the BiMPPI components.

enables changing the spin direction of the motors and, consequently, the collective thrust direction of the platform, allowing it to push against the pipeline and ensure contact during the rotational inspection around it. In addition, the generated torque by using bidirectional motors is greater than unidirectional motors, allowing for greater control torque during the rotation.

As presented in Section 1, the BiMPPI mounts two landing gears, one on the bottom and another on the top, for performing full or half perimeter pipe inspections. The bottom one is a 3D-printed landing gear, composed of four legs. Each leg consists of three links: one screwed to the base, an intermediate one, and a final one that makes contact with the pipe. It is circular in shape with an internal radius of 8 cm, allowing it to land on pipes with a diameter of 16 cm. However, since it is composed of three links instead of a single piece, it can be adjusted for larger pipes up to 36 cm. The top one is composed of four straight aluminum legs. This landing gear is not used for landing on the pipe, but for landing on the floor after completing a half-perimeter inspection when the platform is performing a reverse flight. Figure 6 presents both landing gears, including the platform landed on pipes with diameters of 16 cm and 32 cm.

5.2. Autopilot

The complete control framework of the BiMPPI has been developed by modifying the open-source autopilot *ArduPilot*. Figure 8 shows a schematic of the developed autopilot. The standard version of *ArduPilot* includes components such as position and attitude controllers, an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF), and the motor mixer. The position and attitude controllers in the standard *ArduPilot* are based on a cascade structure, similar to the one presented in Section 4.1. The state estimation is obtained using the EKF, which combines measurements from

Figure 8: The BiMPPI control schematic based on the *Ardupilot* autopilot. The modified parts are marked in pink.

an inertial measurement unit (IMU) and the external positioning system, which, in our case, is OptiTrack. Finally, the necessary torque and force are converted into motor PWM signals by the motor mixer, which takes into account the geometric distribution of the motors in the UAV frame.

Similarly, the introduced modifications in *Ardupilot* have been highlighted in pink in Figure 8. Specifically, the attitude control and the motor mixer have been modified, while we have introduced a functionality to switch between three modes: normal flight mode (N), reverse flight mode (R), and inspection mode (I).

In normal flight mode, the controller is the standard *Ardupilot* cascaded PID controller, with the roll equilibrium point at $\phi = 0^\circ$. Additionally, to prevent aggressive maneuvers due to the change in motor direction, the control action of the motors in the motor mixer is restricted to $f_i(t) \in [0, f_{\max}] \forall i = 1, \dots, 4$. In reverse flight mode, the cascaded PID controller of *Ardupilot* is also used. However, the roll equilibrium point has been modified to $\phi(t) = 180^\circ$ for the inverted flight. Similarly, as in normal flight, the motor actions in the motor mixer are restricted to $f_i(t) \in [-f_{\max}, 0] \forall i = 1, \dots, 4$. For the perimeter inspection mode, the attitude controller has been modified to the SDRE controller presented in Section 4.2. In addition, for having a bigger control action, the bi-directionality of the motors is also enabled with $f_i(t) \in [-f_{\max}, f_{\max}] \forall i = 1, \dots, 4$. This force range corresponds to a PWM range of 1000 to 2000, where 1500 generates $f_i = 0$. For the rotational movement, the roll equilibrium point is linearly modified according to $\phi(t) = at$, where a is the roll rate during the inspection. Furthermore, the collective thrust $T(t)$ is fixed in this mode with the radio control (RC), as the position controller is not used. To ensure contact during the operation, the chosen value must satisfy $T(t) > mg$. Finally, since the pitch and yaw angles are determined by the pipeline's orientation, the pitch and yaw controllers are disabled in the inspection mode.

6. Experiments

6.1. Full Perimeter Inspection with Integral SDRE

The BiMPPI is validated through a complete operation where it lands on the pipeline, rotates around it, and takes off after the pipeline perimeter inspection.

Figure 9: Different instants of the full-perimeter inspection performed by the BiMPPI. The video presentation of the experiment is available as supplementary material of the article in the online version at the journal website.

The landing and take-off are conducted manually by a pilot, as the autonomous landing and take-off from the pipeline are out of the scope of this work. The rotation around the pipeline is conducted autonomously with the integral-SDRE controller presented in Section 4. The rotational operation is shown in Figure 9, where the BiMPPI performs a perimeter inspection around a PVC pipeline with an outer diameter of 16 cm. Based on the simulations, the chosen weighting parameters of the SDRE plus integrator are $\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}(1, 1.5)$, $R = 1$ and $K_I = 1$. The position of the platform is given by the motion capture system Optitrack.

The results of the rotational movement around pipeline are shown in Figure 10, where the roll reference is given by $\phi_{\text{ref}}(t) = at$ with $a = 6^\circ \text{s}^{-1}$, and the roll error is defined as $e_\phi(t) = \phi(t) - \phi_{\text{ref}}(t)$. The reference is properly tracked by the controller, achieving a maximal absolute error of $|e_\phi(t)|_{\text{max}} = 11.9^\circ$ and a mean error $\overline{e_\phi(t)} = -2.6^\circ$. The roll-angle error has a sinusoidal shape due to the non-linear generated torque by gravity, as presented in Eq. (23).

Furthermore, the PWM signals are shown in Figure 11, including the three phases of the experiment: landing, inspection, and takeoff. Since the pitch and yaw controllers are disabled during inspection mode, the PWM signals for motors 1-3 and motors 2-4 are the same. Additionally, during landing and takeoff, marked with a red background in the figure, the platform generates a positive collective thrust $T(t) > 0$, as the PWM signals are lower than 1500. However, during the rotation, the direction of the propellers is reversed, and the platform starts to push against the pipeline to ensure contact, as the PWM signals exceed 1500. Specifically, a collective thrust $T(t) = mg + \Delta T$ is set using the RC, where ΔT is 10% of the weight. This value ensures contact with the pipeline throughout the entire operation. Moreover, some motors change the spin direction in certain areas of the inspections, as the PWM signals are lower than 1500. These areas correspond with $\phi = 90^\circ$ and $\phi = 270^\circ$, where the required control torque is at its maximum due to the sinusoidal behavior of the gravitational torque. In addition,

Figure 10: The Roll angle and roll error during the full perimeter inspection. The roll reference changes with a constant rate of $\dot{\phi}_{\text{ref}} = 6^\circ \text{ s}^{-1}$. The roll error is defined as $e_\phi(t) = \phi(t) - \phi_{\text{ref}}(t)$.

Figure 11: PWM signals of the platform during the perimeter inspection. The take-off and landing phases are highlighted with a red background, while the inspection phase is highlighted with a green background.

due to this sinusoidal behavior of the gravitational torque, the PWM signals also have a sinusoidal shape.

Finally, Figure 12 represents the YZ trajectory of the platform during the three phases. The BiMPPI can properly land on the pipe, rotate around it, and take off after the inspection. The OptiTrack cameras stop tracking the markers when the BiMPPI passes through the lower part, as the platform is obscured by the pipeline. This causes spikes in the position estimation. However, these peaks do not influence the controller, as the platform only controls the roll angle, with all other controllers disabled, as indicated in Section 5.

6.2. Controller Comparisons

The integral SDRE controller is compared with the SDRE controller and with the standard PID controller of Ardupilot. To ensure a fair comparison, all con-

Figure 12: YZ trajectory of the platform during the complete inspection process. The operation is divided into three phases: landing (blue), perimeter inspection (red), and take-off (yellow). The outer diameter of the pipeline is depicted by the black dashed line. The peaks in the trajectory during the inspection are attributed to reduced visibility of the OptiTrack markers in the lower part of the pipeline.

trollers were tested under identical experimental conditions. These conditions included using the same platform, pipe (16 cm diameter), reference trajectory ($a = 6^\circ \text{s}^{-1}$), and even ensuring the same battery level for all tests to avoid any potential discrepancies. The maximum roll error $|e_\phi(t)|_{\max}$ and mean roll error $\overline{e_\phi(t)}$ were used as performance metrics for all controllers, providing a direct and unbiased evaluation. Moreover, the weighting matrices of the SDRE and the integral SDRE were selected identically to perform a fair comparison.

Figure 13 presents the results of the three controllers, including the roll error during the operation, while Table 2 presents the roll error metrics for the three controllers. The standard PID controller of Ardupilot is unable to track the roll reference effectively. The PID controller transitions from the unstable equilibrium point at $\phi = 0^\circ$ to the stable equilibrium point at $\phi = 180^\circ$ in response to a high error, as shown in Figure 13. Since the PID controller is unable to track the reference, we stopped the experiment when the platform reached the stable equilibrium point. It can not track the reference because it is designed to track angles close to 0° , as the operation point is $\phi = 0^\circ$. In addition, the controller does not consider the sinusoidal behavior of the equilibrium torque. Due to this, a nonlinear controller is necessary to control the platform during the full rotation.

The behavior of the integral SDRE and the SDRE controller are very similar. Both of them are able to track properly the reference during the complete operation. However, the integral-SDRE controller has a lower maximum absolute error $|e_\phi(t)|_{\max}^{\text{I-SDRE}} = 11.9^\circ$ and mean error $\overline{e_\phi(t)}^{\text{I-SDRE}} = -2.6^\circ$, compared with the SDRE controller $|e_\phi(t)|_{\max}^{\text{SDRE}} = 36.2^\circ$ and $\overline{e_\phi(t)}^{\text{SDRE}} = -15.8^\circ$, as it includes an integral term for reducing the error in terms of existence uncertainty and disturbance in the system.

Controller comparative

Figure 13: Full perimeter inspection using three different controllers: an integral-SDRE controller (blue), an SDRE controller (red), and a standard PID from Ardupilot (yellow). The Ardupilot PID experiment was stopped as it failed to follow the reference and remained at the stable equilibrium point $\phi = 180^\circ$.

Table 2: Comparison of the performance metrics for different controllers.

Controller	$ e_\phi(t) _{\max}$	$\overline{e_\phi(t)}$
Integral SDRE	11.9 °	-2.6 °
SDRE	36.2 °	-15.8 °
PID ArduPilot (Stopped)	Failed	Failed

6.3. Other Scenarios

The BiMPPI can also perform half perimeter inspection due to its bidirectional thrusters. Specifically, the platform can conduct Top-to-Bottom and Bottom-to-Top inspections, which are needed when obstacles beside the pipelines prevent the full rotation. Figure 14 presents the roll angle during these operations, showing that the proposed controller can perform both operations properly. In the Top-to-Bottom inspection (left figure), the platform starts on the pipeline after landing with normal flight and then rotates 180 degrees to take off from the bottom part of the pipeline in an inverted flight. In the Bottom-to-Top inspection (right figure), the platform starts from the bottom part after contacting the pipeline in inverted flight, ascends to the top while rotating, and then takes off from the top part in normal flight.

7. Conclusions

This paper has presented the BiMPPI, a novel multirotor for perimeter pipe inspections based on bidirectional thrusters that allow it to push against the pipeline

Figure 14: Others operations performed by the BiMPPI: Top-to-Bottom inspection rotating from $\phi = 0^\circ$ to $\phi = 180^\circ$ (left figure), and Bottom-to-Top inspection rotating from $\phi = 180^\circ$ to $\phi = 0^\circ$ (right figure).

and perform full perimeter inspections around it. The rotation around a pipe for a UAV releases nonlinear dynamics, which led us to select a nonlinear optimal controller, the SDRE. It is popular for pendulum-like motion control in the literature. The SDRE design uses the nonlinearity of the model in the derivation of the control input, allowing bigger stability margins for regulation control tasks. The traditional SDRE is sensitive to model uncertainty and external disturbance; hence, an integrator was added to the controller to eliminate the steady-state error and provide robustness to the design. An equivalent version of the servo-SDRE was formulated using the exact solution approach combined with an integrator. The results showed the advantages of the integrator in eliminating the steady-state error due to disturbance and uncertainty. The experimental platform is based on a standard quadrotor frame that includes an ESC with bidirectional control capability of the brushless motors. The BiMPPI has been validated through indoor flights where it lands on a PVC pipeline, performs a full rotation around it, and finally takes off. The proposed integral-SDRE controller has shown a superior performance than PID controllers in experimental tests.

Future work includes the autonomous execution of the complete mission, outdoor validation in a real industrial environment, adding an advanced disturbance rejection mechanism to the SDRE, and expanding the inspection capabilities to include inclined or vertical pipelines.

Supplementary Material

The video file of the experiments is provided as the supplementary material of this work in the online version of the paper.

Conflict of interest

None.

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